

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ZIMUTO****FIRST NAME: SHUPIKAYI****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE (1)****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

Seven key concepts:

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 6-14)
2. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
3. America VS. British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Style guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)

WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

1)INTRODUCTION

The internal desire, gut feeling, and conscience of starting a Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) seven years after obtaining my master's degree come with confusion about not knowing where to start. The work pressure, family demands, and orientation documents that all needed my attention were overwhelming at the start as I am studying part-time. I had to study the Student Orientation PDF received in the initial email (which includes other essential files such as the templates and checklists). I did the registration protocols as guided, read the study material for period one, and watched the introductory tutorial videos. I realized this introductory course's importance as I assumed my writing skills were good. Indeed, I established that learning is a lifelong process and that writing an excellent academic essay requires different skills and expertise. This introductory course lays a good foundation for me and will remain helpful throughout my study life and beyond.

My response paper will discuss five major concepts I learned from the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack (period 1) and essential tutorial video guides. The concepts are essay writing, punctuation, American VS British English, plagiarism, and style guide.

2) ESSAY WRITING

Writing an academic essay requires one to know the basics of writing, understand the steps for writing a good essay and know the rule of thumbs for writing a paper. The first chapter of the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack focus on articulating this. EUCLID (2021, 7) defines an academic essay or scholarly writing as nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work. Examples of academic writing include research findings or reports on empirical fieldwork which may not or may be published in journals, books, newspapers, or other periodicals. In my understanding, the simple goal of an academic essay is to provide information based on facts and the conclusion of the author's research as opposed to the creativity of the writer's imagination. This chapter is a good starting point to prepare me for subsequent periods and gives a glimpse of the approach to future writing throughout my Doctor of Philosophy study courses.

The planning process is critical in writing an essay. That is, one should start on time, understand the question and task, and draft a clear plan for the essay. I will always draft a writing plan before writing an essay, as this helps me focus and deliver the task on time.

I have also understood that to write a good essay; one must follow the key steps to adequately answer the essay question by providing the necessary evidence and relevant examples. The steps for writing are flexible, and what is essential is for one to ensure that vital aspects of each step are followed, such as essay writing planning, researching the topic and note writing, drafting, editing, and reviewing. I have also understood that sources of facts for academic essays must be credible academic resources, as amplified in (EUCLID 2021, 8; The University of Sydney, n.d.). Furthermore, one must critically read and think to extract meaningful information from credible academic sources. In critical reading, (the University of York, 2022) argues students to identify the writer's claim and how empirical facts support the claim. Critical thinking involves consciously applying established techniques to processing gathered information (Foundation for Critical Thinking, n.d.). Hitchcock (2020) described critical thinking as "careful goal-directed thinking." Critical thinking enables students to apply mental techniques in extracting goal-oriented information from academic resources. Critical reading and thinking are vital in organizing ideas and essay drafting.

The general structure of any essay should follow the format of an introduction first, then the body and the conclusion. Each paragraph in an essay should focus on one aspect or central point to ensure a good flow and avoid confusing readers.

3) PUNCTUATIONS

Punctuation is an important rule that guides effective and consistent academic essay writing. Punctuations convey meanings to sentences (EUCLID 2021, 16). For example, the apostrophe conveys possession of singular nouns or indefinite pronouns. Apostrophes are also used to express contractions of two words in the English language. The bullet symbol

is used in lists of words, phrases, or clauses that complete sentences. Depending on their position in a sentence, the colon and semi-colon determine the meanings of parts of the sentence. While the semi-colon links two related parts of a sentence, the colon connects unrelated parts. Commas have multiple usages conveying meanings in sentences (EUCLID 2021, 19-20). They are used to identify non-defining clauses, words, or phrases according to placement in sentences.

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

In reviewing the course literature, I discovered that despite American English having a dominant influence on “world English” compared to British English, the EUCLID policy accepts both in academic essay writing if one of the two is used consistently throughout the document. Mixing the two is not allowed. EUCLID (2021,25) states that American and British English are variants of World English. As such, they are more similar than different, especially with “educated” or “scientific” English. Most divergence can be ascribed to differing national histories and cultural developments and how the two national variants have changed correspondingly. Therefore, I will adopt British English because I am a Zimbabwean, a former British colony.

EUCLID (2021, 25) revealed that the two variants (American and British English) may have different spellings of some words but the same pronunciation or vice-versa. Further, some words may be the same spelling but may convey additional meanings when used in some contexts. Other differences include the usage of punctuation, collective nouns, and plural adjectives. In this regard, it is important to be consistent with one variant when writing academic essays to avoid confusing the readers.

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is one of the most crucial aspects of essay writing. According to EUCLID (2021, 34), plagiarism is when a writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. In my view, this definition resonates with Merriam–Webster dictionary, which defines plagiarism as a) The theft and use of other people's ideas or words as yours; b) Use of sources without attribution; c) Literary theft, and d) presenting some ideas as own and as it is new, while this idea already exists in other sources. I have learnt that plagiarism creates legal and ethical problems for writers, intentionally or unintentionally, and should be taken seriously as it has serious consequences.

Fortunately, there are ways to avoid plagiarism and tools available to detect plagiarism, such as software. It is prudent to cite the authors or source of information one has used. Furthermore, one can avoid plagiarism by using text citations, quotations, and paraphrasing. EUCLID (2021,36) describes paraphrases as the ideas and information that an author has produced on a topic but written in your own words. Paraphrasing is a way to

avoid too many quotes, which must look completely different from what the original author wrote. Paraphrasing can also help bring better clarity.

I have also learnt that in fear of avoiding plagiarism, it is not everything that one must cite or reference. If the information one is writing is common knowledge, then citing is unnecessary.

6)STYLE GUIDE

In general, style guides provide a set of rules and guidelines to be followed in writing to ensure consistency and meet the expectations of an organization or institution in the documentation and expression of ideas. Euclid University recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian) but also accepts other internationally recognized rules in academic essays. The expected consistency may include preferred sentence lengths, manuscript layout, font usage, depth of treatment of a subject, spelling (UK v US example), readership consideration, use of abbreviations, accepted terminology, use of symbols, voices preferences (active v passive), structure, and many more EUCLID (2021, 41). Style guides usually come with templates that an organization recommends to stakeholders to achieve coherence and consistency. Style guides are essential, especially for publications, academic writing, business writing, and technical writing, and preferences on which style guides also differ.

I have used the University of Oxford Style guide in my essay writing. It is rich in context, handy, and broad in usage, covering language elements and writing styles. However, following my review of the Chicago Rules (Turabian), I have noted another different perspective. I concur with EUCLID (2021, 41), which argued that the lack of a single authoritative source on style for written English means there is, and will always be, a certain amount of debate on style elements.

7)CONCLUSION

Reading through this introductory period study materials and watching the short and interactive videos was an enriching experience for me. This study period has made me understand that writing academic essays requires many skills, knowledge of specific processes, rules, and guidelines on punctuation, avoiding plagiarism, consistent use of one English variant, and style guide. This course pack remains a valuable document for the entire period of my study and beyond. I will continue reading and applying it whenever I write academic essays.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Hitchcock, David. n.d. "Critical Thinking." Accessed April 20, 2023. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2020/entries/critical-thinking>.

The University of Sydney. n.d. "What are sources?" Accessed April 20, 2023. <https://canvas.sydney.edu.au/courses/12076/pages/what-are-sources>.

University of York. 2022. "Critical Reading." Accessed April 20, 2023. <https://subjectguides.york.ac.uk/skills/critical-reading>.

The Foundation for Critical Thinking. n.d. "Defining Critical Thinking." Accessed April 20, 2023. <https://www.criticalthinking.org/pages/defining-critical-thinking/766>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.